

Research Article

Effect of Different Irrigation Water Regime on Cucumber Yield and Water Use under Sprinkler System

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Abstract

*A research study was conducted on irrigation research field in National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization, NCAM, Ilorin, Nigeria to determine the effect of different irrigation water regime on cucumber (*Cucumis sativus* L.) yield, water use efficiency and irrigation water use efficiency. Cucumber grown under field condition using sprinkler irrigation system on an irrigation research field showed good production responses. Yield of cucumber was reasonably appreciable when the crop was administered with a total quantity of 100 % of crop water need at different sensitivity stages. The treatment with minimum irrigation water applied had the lowest productions with the fruits showing irregular and oblong shapes instead of usual shapes. Fresh fruit yields were highly influenced by the total volume of irrigation water at every growth stage. From the analysis of the result carried out, it was established that the fresh yield of cucumber decreases when irrigation water applied falls below optimum crop water need. The water use efficiency was directly related to the fresh fruit yield, while the irrigation water use efficiency was inversely related to crop evapotranspiration as evident from establishment stage to vegetative stage of cucumber production.*

Keywords: irrigation, yield, evapotranspiration, crop water use, water use efficiency.

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Introduction

Cucumber (*Cucumis sativus L.*) is one of the most popular and widely grown vegetables crops in the world and it belongs to the family Cucurbitacea. It is a typical vegetable that grows in warm, temperate and cool tropical areas (Maas and Hoffman, 1977). Due to its increase demand, it is considered as one of the most important economic vegetables. From various researches carried out on the crop, it was established that it requires more water than grain crops (Li and Wang, 2000, Mao *et al.*, 2003). Mao *et al.* (2003) found that fresh fruit yields of cucumber were highly affected by the total volume of irrigation water at all growth stages.

The production of cucumber during dry season is encouraged for availability of fresh vegetables, even though its production during rainy season in some areas makes it a seasonal vegetable. Despite the fact that traditional farmers rely on their experiences to irrigate cucumber such as furrow and basin irrigation which do not in most cases actually result into expected high yield with its attendant drudgery. The production of cucumber can be enhanced with adequate knowledge of crop water use and the application of irrigation water at the appropriate stages of growth. The use of irrigation techniques such as sprinkler is inevitable for vegetable production in the near future because of the salinity problem caused by traditional irrigation methods. Researchers have found out that excessive watering and improper irrigation techniques leads to non-uniform distribution of water in crop field with reduced yield (Phene *et al.*, 1979; Papadopoulos, 1991).

Being aware of the water sensitivity of plant species on their responses to water, there is a need to choose the most suitable irrigation method and scheduling for them based on the source and availability of water (Meiri *et al.*, 1992). Gao, (1994) in his findings of cucumber plants revealed that they possess moderate deep roots and shallow fibrous root system which makes them efficient user of available moisture within the top 60 cm of soil layer. Timely and adequate application of irrigation water is necessary for good yield increase in farming practices. Hence, it is important to determine the growth period when plants are susceptible to water usage in order to avoid water stress and optimize the yield from irrigated area. Previous studies have shown that fairly good knowledge of crop water use have resulted into proper irrigation scheduling to save water and increase yield. (Zhang *et al.*, 2011; Oweis *et al.*, 2000; Pandey *et al.*, 2000; Motilva *et al.*, 2000; Li *et al.*, 2001; Fabeiro *et al.*, 2001).

The use of Class A pan for irrigation programming has been stressed when there are available crop coefficients in hand. Kenber (1984) revealed that there is a close

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relationship between the plant water consumption and pan evaporation. Therefore evapotranspiration of grown plants can be deduced by pan evaporation with the help of predetermined coefficients (Doorenbos and Pruitt, 1975). Moreover, class A pan is commonly used due to the fact that it is the most suitable and resultant system for the plant, water and climate relationship.

In order to get optimum plant yield, application of adequate and appropriate amount of water needed for the plant is essential for development of most suitable irrigation schedule. Erroneous irrigation applications underestimating irrigation amount and quantity may cause yield decrease as affirmed by Ertek *et al.*, (2002). It is therefore imperative to determine the right amount of water supplies needed for plant growth during the vegetation period. Ertek *et al.*, (2002) concluded from his research work that yield increase in intensive farming practices during dry season mostly depends on timely and adequate application of irrigation water needed for plant growth.

The purpose of this study was to demonstrate the effect of different irrigation regimes on the yield, water use efficiency and irrigation water use efficiency at different growth stages of cucumber under field condition.

Materials and Methods

This study was carried out in an irrigation research field established at National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) Ilorin, Nigeria during irrigation research period of year 2016. Six plots of cucumber plantation were used for the experiment with the area of each plot as 5 m x 10 m. Crops were irrigated with the use of sprinkler irrigation system that lasted through the period of experiment that lasted between January and April. The amount of irrigation water applied to each plot was controlled and monitored by the use of gate valve and a water meter respectively.

In determining the amount of applied irrigation water (I_r), pan evaporation whose fundamentals are given in the articles of Doorenbos and Pruitt (1975); Kanber (1984) were used.

$$I_r = A \cdot E_{\text{pan}} k_c \quad 1$$

Where I_r is the amount of applied irrigation water, A is the plot area, E_{pan} is the cumulative pan evaporation at irrigation, and k_c is the crop pan coefficient.

Evaporation within the irrigation period was measured with a class -A pan in the NCAM weather station. Crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) was calculated for the crop in each plot

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by determining the reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_o) value using empirical relationship with measured data from weather station of NCAM Meteorological Automatic Weather System in conjunction with the crop coefficient (k_c) as expressed in the equations below

$$ET_o = k_p E_{pan} \quad 2$$

$$ET_c = ET_o k_c \quad 3$$

Where ET_c is the crop evapotranspiration, k_c is the crop pan coefficient, ET_o is the reference crop evapotranspiration, k_p is the pan coefficient, and E_{pan} is the pan evaporation.

Irrigation water use efficiency and water use efficiency (Vites,1962; Stanhill, 1986) were calculated as follows:

$$IWUE = Y_a/ET_c \quad 4$$

$$WUE = Y_a/I_r \quad 5$$

Where : IWUE is the irrigation water use efficiency, WUE is the water use efficiency, Y_a is the actual yield of a given plot and I_r is the amount of applied irrigation water.

The amount of irrigation water applied was calculated separately for each plot by using equation 1. Cucumber is a quick growing crop that produces a lot of succulent growth; it requires plenty of moisture for its vigorous growth. Since the experiment was performed during the dry season, adequate moisture was supplied to all the plots to enhance germination of the seeds. After the establishment of the crops, scheduled irrigation application was then administered to the plots as designed for different regimes of irrigation water. Additional irrigation water was varied in the order of 50 % to 100 % of calculated crop water need (ET_c) to the six different plots. All plots were watered at different irrigation water regime level during the decade (ten day) period of application of water in each sensitivity stages and scheduled irrigation of 2 day interval were initiated for all the plots with varying quantity of irrigation water.

Results and Discussions

Tables 1 and 2 show the computed values of pan evaporation (E_{pan}), reference crop evapotranspiration (ET_o) and crop evapotranspiration (ET_c) for cucumber during the experimental period. The pan coefficient was taken to be 0.75 (FAO, 1984) and the crop coefficient varied from 0.45 to 1.25 as given by Kenber (1986). From the result of data obtained from Table 3, irrigation water was applied to the plots in varying amount, right from 100 % of crop water need (ET_c) to 50 %, indicating various regime of water

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application on various sensitivity stages. Each stage lasted within a period of thirty days. Under one and half month, cucumber smaller plant seedlings require less water compared to flowering stage when there was an increase in ET as indicated in Table 2. After the cucumber fruit appearance on stems, more cucumber plants blossomed and more fruits appeared. Plants needed more water to meet the needs of more succulent fruits and higher soil evaporation so water requirement increased drastically towards yield formation.

Table 1. Decade (10 days) values of E_{pan} , ET_c and k_c for cucumber

Decade	E_{pan} (mm)	ET_o	k_c	ET_c
1	56.5	42.375	0.45	19.07
2	108.4	81.3	0.5	40.65
3	54.7	41.025	0.7	28.72
4	44.4	33.3	0.75	24.98
5	62.5	46.875	0.9	42.19
6	39	29.25	1.0	29.25
7	41.7	31.275	1.25	39.09
8	80.5	60.375	1.2	72.45
9	69.3	51.975	1.0	51.97
10	22.1	16.575	0.75	12.43
11	27.9	20.925	0.7	14.65
12	82.2	61.65	0.5	30.83

From the analysis of data from Table 3, the higher the amount of irrigation water applied the higher fresh fruits of cucumber obtained. A total of twenty-four harvest period were made during the experiment with average harvest of four times per plot of six. Each cucumber fruit was weighed in each harvest to determine fruit weight per plot. From the analysis of yield of different plot under different water regime, plot 1 was with the highest yield and the yield decreased to plot 6 due to decrease in irrigation water applied. The yield of plots 5 and 6 were not only small but the fruits were oblong and irregular shaped as compared to other yields.

Table 2. Monthly values of E_{pan} , k_c and ET_c for cucumber

Month	E_{pan} (mm)	ET_o	k_c	ET_c
January	219.6	164.7	0.55	90.585
February	145.9	109.43	0.88	96.298
March	191.5	143.63	1.15	165.17
April	132.2	99.15	0.65	64.45

IWUE and WUE were calculated as fresh fruit cucumber yield divided by crop evapotranspiration and irrigation water applied volume respectively as shown in table 3. WUE decreases with decrease in yield, while IWUE decreases with increase in ET_c on different sensitivity stages. The reason for I_r greater than ET_c in all the treatment was due to the fact that the irrigation water applied to the crops was more than the crop's water need. Highest value of WUE was found in plot 1 which indicated that water was used effectively in this plot.

Conclusions

Irrigation systems are essential for water application to the field during dry season farming so as to reduce the drudgery of applying water traditionally. The use of sprinkler system for irrigating cucumber during dry season has proved to be worthwhile from this study. However, optimal use of water to meet crop requirement at any stage of growth has also resulted into appreciable level of yield as demonstrated in different yield obtained from different regime of irrigation water applied to the crop.

Therefore, cucumber grown in irrigated condition showed good production responses. From the result of the experiment carried out so far, it can be inferred that yield is considerably appreciable when cucumber receives a total quantity of 100 % of crop water need below which there are noticeable decrease in yield as the water regime decreases. Even though, the experiment has not established the optimum water use for irrigating cucumber that will give the optimum yield during dry season farming, the result has shown that the fresh yields decreases when irrigation falls below 100 % of crop water need. This simply showed that moderate irrigation is essential. The analysis of water applied in each of crop's growth stages made it possible to classify their effects on the development of the yield.

Table 3. Different Irrigation Water Regime on Cucumber during growth

Sensitivity stages	k_c	ET_c (m^3m^{-2})	Plot 1	Plot 2	Plot 3	Plot 4	Plot 5	Plot 6	IWUE
			(+100%)	(+90%)	(+80%)	(+70%)	(+60%)	(+50%)	
Establishment	0.5	0.029	I_{r1} (m^3)	I_{r2} (m^3)	I_{r3} (m^3)	I_{r4} (m^3)	I_{r5} (m^3)	I_{r6} (m^3)	
Vegetative	0.75	0.027	1.854	1.851	1.848	1.845	1.842	1.839	46.03
Flowering	1.0	0.04	1.850	1.847	1.844	1.841	1.839	1.836	67.52
Yield formation	1.25	0.041	2.44	2.436	2.432	2.428	2.424	2.42	60
Total Irr. Water applied (I_{rT})			2.791	2.787	2.783	2.779	2.775	2.771	67.07
Actual yield (Y_a) (kg)			8.935	8.921	8.907	8.893	8.88	8.866	
WUE (kgm^{-3})			68	24	19	12.4	4.55	3.29	
			7.61	2.69	2.13	1.39	0.51	0.37	

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